

The prediction of the composite joint strength using the failure area index method

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With the wide application of fiber-reinforced composite material in aero-structures and mechanical parts, the design of composite joint have become a very important research area because they are often the weakest areas in composite structures. In this paper, the failure area index method to predict the strength of the mechanically fastened composite joint which has the same stacking sequence was suggested and evaluated. By the suggested failure area index method, the strengths of the mechanically fastened composite joints which have the different geometric shapes, dimensions, hole size and stacking sequence could be predicted within 9.96 %.

KEY WORDS : composite joint, failure criterion

1. Introduction

The fiber reinforced composite materials has been widely used in aircraft, space structures because of their high specific modulus and high specific strength [1]. As composites have become popular in recent years, the design of the composite joint has become a very important research area because the structural efficiency of the composite structure is determined by its joints, not by its basic structures. Generally, the joining methods of the composite structures are classified into mechanical and adhesive types. The adhesive joints do not require holes and they distribute the load over larger area than mechanical joints. However, they are very sensitive to the surface treatment, service temperature, humidity and other environmental conditions [2,3].

In this paper, the method to predict the failure load of the mechanically fastened composite joint was studied. Several strength prediction methods for mechanically fastened joints have been proposed. Chamis [4] has studied the variation of the joint strength on the geometric shapes and the laminate strength. Hart-Smith [5] has used the stress concentration coefficient for the prediction of the mechanically fastened joint. Whitney and Nuismer [6, 7] have suggested the characteristic length based on the average stress criterion and the failure criterion. Chang et al. [8, 9] have suggested the characteristic curve generated by the combination of the characteristic lengths for tension and compression. Hollman [10] has suggested the damage zone model based on the fracture energy and progressive failure analysis. However, these prediction methods are very complex and most of them need the standard coupon tests or the special codes for prediction of failure load. Therefore, the simple method to predict the

composite joint strength by the commercial finite element software without extra coupon tests has been required.

In this paper, the failure area index method to predict the failure load of the mechanically fastened composite joint which has the same stacking sequence was suggested. The failure loads of the composite joint on the geometric shapes and dimensions were predicted by the failure area index method and compared with the experimental results.

2. Test specimen and experimental results

The 7-type joint models which have the different ratios of the w/d (width to hole diameter) and l/d (edge length to hole diameter) were manufactured and tested. The carbon epoxy uni-directional prepreg and plane weave prepreg were used. The stacking sequences of the specimens were $[\pm 45_3/90/\pm 45_2/0_4/90/0_4/\pm 45_2/90/\pm 45_3]$ and $[0_2/45/-45/90_2/0_2]_S$. The “ ± 45 ” notation implies the plane weave carbon/epoxy layer.

Figure 1 shows the geometric shapes of the composite joint specimens and their dimensions are shown in Table 1. The tungsten carbide drills were used for machining of the hole and they were discarded after a single usage to reduce the effects on the cutting conditions. Figure 2 shows the double lap joint jig for measuring the failure load of the composite joint. The composite joint specimens were tested in a Universal Machine 8516 of INSTRON Co. at cross head speed of 1mm/min. The eight times tensile tests on each model were conducted and the average value of them was calculated. From the tests, the net-tension failure mode occurred in the M02, R02 specimens as shown in Figure 3 (a). Also, the M04, S02 specimens had the shear-out failure mode as shown in Figure 3 (b) and the others had the bearing failure mode as shown in Figure 3 (c).

3. Failure area index method

The strengths of the mechanically fastened composite joints calculated by the failure criterions such as Tsai-Wu, Yamada-Sun will be underestimated due to the stress concentration around a hole of the composite joint. The characteristic length method can be considered to estimate whether the failure occurs at a certain distance apart from a hole of the composite joint. In this paper, the failure area index method to estimate the average failure index at a certain area was suggested. A certain area A_i can be considered to have the high possibility of the failure and can be defined as area in which the failure index F of an individual laminar is larger than unity.

The failure index F of the Tsai-Wu and Yamada-Sun criterion can be calculated as follows.

Tsai-Wu Failure criterion

$$F = F_i \sigma_i + F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j \quad (i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 6) \quad (1)$$

$$F_{11} = \frac{1}{X_T} - \frac{1}{X_C} ; F_{22} = \frac{1}{Y_T} - \frac{1}{Y_C} ; F_{111} = \frac{1}{X_T X_C} ; F_{222} = \frac{1}{Y_T Y_C}$$

$$F_{33} = 0 ; F_{44} = \frac{1}{R^2} ; F_{55} = \frac{1}{S^2} ; F_{66} = \frac{1}{T^2} ; F_{12} = -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{X_T X_C Y_T Y_C}}$$

X_T : Longitudinal tensile strength
 X_C : Longitudinal compressive strength
 Y_T : Transverse tensile strength
 Y_C : Transverse compressive strength
 S : Shear strength

Yamada-Sun Failure criterion

$$F = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

The failure area index FAI can be expressed as follows.

$$FAI = \frac{\int F^n dA}{H_A} \approx \frac{\sum F_i^n \cdot A_i}{H_A} \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots) \quad (3)$$

FAI : Failure Area Index
 n : Weighting factor
 F : Failure Index
 H_A : Interior area of a hole

In the failure area index method, it is assumed that the failure of the composite joint occurs when the FAI reaches a certain reference value. The weighting factor n of Equation (3) play a role of weighting of failure index with respect to the area and the interior area of a hole H_A is proportional to the joint size and play a role of correction coefficient on the joint size.

To investigate the applicability of the failure area index method, the failure loads of the M01 - M07 models as shown in Figure 1 (a) were identified. To predict the failure load of the composite joint by the failure area index method, the reference value of FAI should be calculated. The M01 model for the reference value of FAI was selected in this paper. Figure 4 shows a half finite element model of the M01 specimen. The contact pair elements were used for the nonlinear contact between the pin and the hole.

From the tests, the failure load of the M01 model was 10.282 kN, it was applied to the finite element model of the composite joint and the failure indexes of an individual lamina were calculated. Figure 5 shows the areas in which the Tsai-Wu failure index of an individual lamina are larger than unity when the failure load was applied. The FAI values by the Tsai-Wu failure criterion and Yamada-Sun failure criterion were 1.2859

and 0.1303, respectively when the weighting factor n was 1. The reference FAI values by Tsai-Wu and Yamada-Sun failure criteria are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 7 shows the failure load of the composite joint predicted by the failure area index method. As shown in Figure 7, the failure loads of the composite joints could be predicted within -9.3% and it was found that the weighting factor n did not have an effect on the prediction accuracy of the failure load. Also, it was found that the prediction accuracies of Figure 7 (b) using the Yamada-Sun failure criterion were better than those of Figure 7 (a) using the Tsai-Wu failure criterion.

Since the failure load of composite joint predicted by the failure area index method can be varied with the selection of failure criterion, it is important to select the most effective failure criterion of the composite joint. For selecting the most effective failure criterion, the tensile failure analysis of the laminate without a hole was performed and compared to the experimental results. Figure 8 shows the calculated failure index of each ply when the experimental tensile load of the laminate without a hole was applied. As shown in Figure 8, it was found that the Yamada-Sun failure criterion was more effective than Tsai-Wu failure criterion because the maximum failure index of the Yamada-Sun came close to unity more than that of the Tsai-Wu. From the analyses of Figure 7 and 8, it might be concluded that the most effective failure criterion that can predict the failure load of the simple tension specimen should be used for the failure area index method.

In order to investigate the prediction accuracy of the failure load on the edge geometry of the composite joint, the failure loads of the composite joints with the rectangular edge as shown in Figure 1 (b) were tested and evaluated. The dimensions of the composite joints with the rectangular edge are shown in Table 1. Figure 9 shows the failure load of the composite joint predicted by the failure area index. The weighting factor was fixed to 1 and the Yamada-Sun failure criterion was used. As shown in Figure 9, the failure loads of the composite joints could be predicted within -6.22 %.

To investigate the prediction accuracy of the failure load on the size of the composite joint, the failure loads of the composite joints which have the same w/d and l/d ratios as those of the M01 model but have different hole diameters were tested and evaluated. The composite joints which have 0.5 times and 1.5 times hole diameters of the M01 model were tested. Figure 10 shows the failure load of the composite joint predicted by the failure area index. As shown in Figure 10, the failure loads of the composite joints could be predicted within 8.72 %.

In order to investigate the applicability of the failure area index method on the variation of the stacking sequence, the failure loads of the S01 - S07 models which have the stacking sequence of $[0_2/45/-45/90_2/0_2]_S$ were tested and evaluated. To predict the failure load of the composite joint which have the different stacking sequence by the failure area index method, the reference value of FAI should be recalculated. The S01 model for the reference value of FAI was selected. From the tests, the failure load of the S01 model was 4.336 kN, it was applied to the finite element analysis. From the experiment and analysis, the reference FAI value by the Yamada-Sun failure criterion was determined to be 0.2030. Figure 11 shows the failure load of the composite joint predicted by the failure area index. As shown in Figure 11, the failure loads of the composite joints could be predicted within 9.96 %.

4. Conclusions

From the study on the failure area index method to predict the failure load of the mechanically fastened composite joint which has the same stacking sequence, the following conclusions can be made:

1. The failure loads of the mechanically fastened composite joint could be predicted within 9.96% by the failure area index method.
2. The most effective failure criterion that can predict the failure load of the simple tension specimen should be used for the failure area index method.

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Table 1. Dimensions of the test specimens.

Model (M*, R**, S***)	01	02	03	04	05	06	07
w (mm)	26.8	19	38	26.8	26.8	26.8	26.8
e (mm)	13.4	13.4	13.4	9.6	19	23.8	28.6
d (mm)	9.53	9.53	9.53	9.53	9.53	9.53	9.53
s (mm)	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
w/d	2.8	2	4	2.8	2.8	2.8	2.8
e/d	1.4	1.4	1.4	1	2	2.5	3

M* : Round edge, $[\pm 45_3/90/\pm 45_2/0_4/90/0_4/\pm 45_2/90/\pm 45_3]$

R** : Rectangular edge, $[\pm 45_3/90/\pm 45_2/0_4/90/0_4/\pm 45_2/90/\pm 45_3]$

S*** : Rectangular edge, $[0_2/45/-45/90_2/0_2]_s$

(a) Round edge [M]

(b) Rectangular edge [R, S]

Figure 1. Dimension of the joint specimen.

Figure 2. Jig for composite joint test.

(A) Net-Tension failure mode

(B) Shear-Out failure mode

(C) Bearing failure mode

Figure 3. Types of the failure modes.

Figure 4. Configuration of the contact element.

Figure 5. Tsai-Wu failure indexes of each ply when the failure Load was applied to the composite joint.

Figure 6. Reference failure area index of the M 01 model.

	M02 (kN)	M03 (kN)	M04 (kN)	M05 (kN)	M06 (kN)	M07 (kN)
Experiment	9.76	10.81	8.01	12.27	11.79	11.63
Tsai-Wu (n=1)	9.66	10.46	7.26	11.48	11.78	11.72
Tsai-Wu (n=2)	9.57	10.50	7.41	11.48	11.78	11.73
Tsai-Wu (n=3)	9.45	10.54	7.57	11.52	11.78	11.75

(a) Tsai-Wu

	M02 (kN)	M03 (kN)	M04 (kN)	M05 (kN)	M06 (kN)	M07 (kN)
Experiment	9.76	10.81	8.01	12.27	11.79	11.63
Yamada-Sun (n=1)	9.40	10.60	8.48	11.53	11.98	12.04
Yamada-Sun (n=2)	9.36	10.60	8.46	11.53	12.00	12.05
Yamada-Sun (n=3)	9.34	10.61	8.44	11.55	12.01	12.07

(b) Yamada-Sun

Figure 7. Failure loads of the composite joint predicted by failure area index method.

Figure 8. Failure index of the tensile test specimen under the ultimate tensile load.

Figure 9. Failure load of the composite joint predicted by the failure area index method.

Figure 10. Failure load of the composite joint predicted by the failure area index method.

Figure 11. Failure load of the composite joint predicted by the failure area index method.